

**EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF TEACHER TRAINEES ON
THEIR TEACHING COMPETENCY**

Education

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INTRODUCTION

Education is the only means with a society to adjust with its needs. Education Is long term investment to achieve the goal or goals, therefore, a society can never exist without education. Through the education, the members of a society learn the skills to enrich, transmit and transform the cultural heritage as well as existing social and scientific knowledge for the continuous advancement of the society.

Today nation with better education system has better mind to work for the development or advancement on this earth or in universe so an effective education system is must to meet the challenges of modern age. The training programme for teachers in India started in the Vedic period in Gurukuls where the father trained the son to be an effective teacher for further generation. Formal training of teachers in modern India started in the 18th century in the form of monitorial mode as operative in India. The Wood's dispatch of 1854 stressed on the training of teachers. Wood's dispatch (1854) desired to see the establishment, with us little delay as possible of training schools and classes or masters in each presidency in India

The recommendation of the Calcutta University Commission (1917) was the hallmark in the development of teacher education in India. The commission recommended the opening of a department of Teacher Education in University to be manned by a Professor, Reader and Lecturers, Mysore was the first to have a faculty of Education in 1925. In India, out of the 18 universities till 1932, 13 had the department of education and Bombay (Mumbai) was the first to launch on M.Ed. programme in 1936.

NEED AND IMPORANCE OF THE STUDY :

No nation can develop without the proper development of it's citizens. The citizens are moulded by the teachers and teachers are prepared through teacher training programme. The strength of educational system depends upon the quality of teachers. The quality of education depends on the quality of teachers. The quality of teachers depends on the quality of teacher training programmes. The quality of teaching learning process is much influenced by the personality and emotional intelligence of teacher educators. The success of teacher education institution depends upon the cordial relationship between teaching competency and psychological variables emotional intelligence.

The researcher wants to investigate Effect of Emotional intelligence of teacher trainees on their Teaching competency. The society is changing very fast. The new inventions and

discoveries are influencing not only the society but the educational system also. On the other hand EI has recently emerged as another non-academic intelligence to help explain life differences independent cognitive abilities. Although the precursors to EI were conceptualized within the theories of Social Intelligences and Personal Intelligences, the term was in fact referenced as early as 1966 and one of the first definitive references to EI was made in 1986 in an unpublished dissertation by Wayne Payne. He distinguished EI from more cognitive forms of intelligence, by describing EI as: "The facts, meanings, truths, relationships etc., are those not exist in the real aim of emotion.

Goleman (1995) has been largely responsible for the widespread popularization of term "Emotional Intelligence" through the publication of his books. Goleman has moulded his own overarching theory of EI based on drawing together his observations and conclusions from the work of other researchers. Historically speaking, the term EI was introduced in 1990 by two American University professors Mayer and Salovey in their attempts to develop a scientific measure for knowing the differences in people's ability in the areas of emotions. However, the credit for popularizing the concept of EI goes to another American Psychologist Daniel Goleman (1995).

"Emotional intelligence is the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our relationships".
Goleman (1998)

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The teaching competency of the teacher trainees has drawn attention of psychologists, educationists, and researchers. It is true that several psychological factors are related to the teaching competency of teacher trainees, but in the present study researcher will make his efforts to identify the relationship with emotional intelligence of teacher trainees. So the problem of the study may be stated as investigate "*Effect of Emotional intelligence of teacher trainees on their Teaching competency.*

TEACHING COMPETENCY:

Teaching competency refers to the set of knowledge, abilities and beliefs a teacher possesses and brings to the teaching situation. Teacher competence differs from teacher's performance and teacher effectiveness in fact it is a stable characteristics of the teacher that does not change appreciably when the teacher moves from one situation to another. Both teacher competence and teacher performance are used as basis from which teacher-effectiveness can be inferred. The skills used by the teachers in the class can be broadly grouped under three major categories.(a)Planning (Pre-instructional) (b) Presentation (Instructional) (c) Closing (d)Evaluation (e)Managerial

TEACHER TRAINEES :

Teacher trainees are those student who are studying in N.C.T.E recognized B.Ed programme of Govt aided institutions affiliated to Lucknow University.

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE:

Emotional Intelligence is one of the latest "buzz words" in education. The major skill that make up emotional intelligence are:

A-Self-awareness, B-Empathy, C-Self-motivation, D-Emotional stability, E Managing relations, F-Integrity, G-Self-development, H-Value orientation, I-Commitment, J-Altruistic behaviour.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

Limitations are potential weaknesses in the study and are out of control. We find limitations in almost everything we do. For emotional intelligence tests and teacher competency the information is only as good as the test itself. Another limitation is time. A study conducted over a certain interval of time is a snapshot dependent on conditions occurring during that time.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The objectives of the present study are as under:

1. To find out the level of emotional intelligence of teachers trainees and its relation to teaching competency.
2. To find out the difference between male and female teachers trainees in relation to their teaching competency and emotional intelligence.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:

To achieve the objectives the following null-hypotheses will be formulated and tested:

- H01. Teachers trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group do not differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency.
- H02. Male teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group do not differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency.
- H03. Female teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group do not differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency.

METHOD OF THE STUDY:

Survey method of research will be used for the present study.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY:

The emotional intelligence of teacher trainees with regard to their teaching competency which will be identified through the investigation undertaken might be applicable to the aided and self-financed institutions, but to make the study feasible, the teacher trainees of N.C.T.E recognized B.Ed programme of aided institutions affiliated to Lucknow University U.P. State will be chosen by lottery method .

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY:

A sample as the name implies is a smaller representation of a larger, where the observation of same phenomenon in competency would involve such a mass of data. In present investigation the researcher will choose a sample of 10 male and 10 female teacher trainees Of N.C.T.E recognized B.Ed programme of 3 aided institutions situated in Lucknow region affiliated to Lucknow University, Lucknow. In sample from each college 10 male and 10 female ie total 60teacher trainees will be selected.

TOOLS TO BE USED:

1. **Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS):** The tool designed by Anukool hyde(Indore), Sanjyot Pethi (Ahemdabad), Upinder Dhar (Indore).
2. **General Teaching Competency Scale (GTCS):** constructed by B.K. Passi and M.S. Lalitha.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE TO BE USED:

The researcher will use appropriate statistical techniques to analysis the data. However, the researcher proposes the ANOVA statistical techniques for the analysis of data. For the purpose of present study ANOVA method will be used to teaching competency of teacher trainees in relation to their emotional intelligence.

STD RELATED TO TEACHING COMPETENCY:

Goyal J. (2013). Conducted a study to find the relationship between creativity and teaching competency of prospective B.Ed. Teachers.

The findings of this study were that:-

- (1) Age below 22 of prospective B.Ed. teachers, found better than age above 22 in their classroom Management, teaching aids, extra Curricular Activities. Communication, Teaching Methodology, ethics of Teaching. Rapport with students and Teaching competency.
- (2) Urban area prospective B.Ed. teachers found between than rural area prospective B.Ed. Teachers.
- (3) There was no significant relationship between teaching competency and creativity of prospective B.Ed. Teachers.

On the basis of this review it may be concluded the role of teacher competencies is very important in the liking pupils of their teaching behaviour.

STD RELATED TO EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE:

- **Kumar Dinesh (2014).** “Emotional intelligence and academic achievement of college students”. The present study was conducted to know the emotional intelligence and academic achievement of college students of Rohini in Delhi. The sample of 100 college students was taken (50 boys and 50 girls) form Rohini. The study indicated that the emotional intelligence of (Science, Art and Commerce stream) college boys and girls were similar while the academic achievement of science boys and girls were not similar, and study also indicated that there was positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

Organization of sample from Govt-aided colleges

S /No	Name of the college	No of male teacher trainees	No of Female teacher trainees	Total
1	LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY CAMPUS	10	10	20
2	LUCKNOW CHRISTIAN TRAINING COLLEGE	10	10	20
3	JAI NARAIN P.G COLLEGE	10	10	20
	TOTAL	30	30	60

INTERPRETATION OF DATA:

Objective No. 1. : To find out the level of emotional intelligence of teacher trainees and its relation to teaching competency.

Hypotheses of the Study :

H01. Teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low level of emotional intelligence group do not differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency.

Table

Analysis of Variance on Teacher Trainees Emotional Intelligence Scores at Different Stages of their Teaching Competency

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	50112.471	2	25056.235	173.365	.01
Within Groups	8238.121	57	144.528		
Total	58350.592	59			

Table Value of F-ratio at (df =2, 117) is F.05= 3.07 and F.01= 4.78

The above Table denotes that analysis of variance has been applied to the **teacher trainees' emotional intelligence scores at different stages of their teaching competency**. The **emotional intelligence scores** of teachers have been divided in the different groups in accordance with their **teaching competency**. The results of the analysis of variance shows that: The calculated value of $F(2,119)=173.365(P<.01)$ for the main effect of teaching competency for exceeds the critical value ($F.01 =4.78$), therefore F-ratio is significant at.01 level. Therefore null hypothesis is rejected and research hypothesis that is 'Teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency, is accepted.

Objective No. 2. : To find out the difference between male and female teacher trainees in relation to their teaching competency and emotional intelligence.

Hypotheses of the Study :

H02. Male teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group do not differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency.

H03. Female teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group do not differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency.

Table

Analysis of Variance on Male Teacher Trainees' Emotional Intelligence Scores at Different Stages of their Teaching Competency

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	31128.124	2	15564.062	92.7227	.01
Within Groups	4532.136	27	167.856		
Total	35660.260	29			

Table Value of F-ratio at (df =2, 57) is F.05= 3.15 and F.01= 4.98

The above Table- denotes that analysis of variance has been applied to the **male teacher trainees' emotional intelligence scores at different stages of their teaching competency**. The

emotional intelligence scores of teacher trainees have been divided in the different groups in accordance with their **teaching competency**. The results of the analysis of variance shows that: The calculated value of $F(2,57) = 92.7227$ ($P < .01$) for the main effect of teaching competency far exceeds the critical value ($F_{.01} = 4.98$), therefore F-ratio is significant at .01 level. Therefore null hypothesis is rejected and research hypothesis that is ‘Male teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency, is accepted.

3. Impact of Teaching Competency upon the Emotional intelligence of Female Teacher Trainees :

Table
Summary Table of Analysis of Variance on Female Teacher Trainees' Emotional Intelligence Scores at Different Stages of their Teaching Competency

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	32451.214	2	16225.607	77.5750	.01
Within Groups	5647.321	27	209.16		
Total	38098.535	29			

Table Value of F-ratio at (df =2, 57) is $F_{.05} = 3.15$ and $F_{.01} = 4.98$

The above Table-4.3 denotes that analysis of variance has been applied to the female **teacher trainees' emotional intelligence scores at different stages of their teaching competency**. The **emotional intelligence scores** of female **teacher trainees** have been divided in the different group sin accordance with their **teaching competency**. The results of the analysis of variance shows that: The calculated value of $F(2,57) = 77.5750$ ($P < .01$) for the main effect of teaching competency far exceeds the critical value ($F_{.01} = 4.98$), therefore F-ratio is significant at .01 level. Therefore null hypothesis is rejected and research hypothesis that is ‘Female teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency, is accepted.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY:

It may be concluded on the basis of the findings that have been found after analyzing the data, that-

- 1 Teaching competency of teacher trainees affects significantly to their** emotional intelligence or in other words Teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency. Further, the mean score of emotional intelligence of teacher trainees having high level of teaching competency is comparatively higher than that of the teacher trainees having average and low level of teaching competency. The mean score of emotional intelligence of teacher trainees having average level of teaching competency is comparatively higher than that of the teacher trainees having low level of teaching competency and is comparatively less than that of the teacher trainees having high level of teaching competency. The mean score of emotional intelligence of teacher trainees having low level of teaching competency is comparatively less than that of the teacher trainees having high and average level of teaching competency.

In addition to that the mean score of emotional intelligence of male teacher trainees is comparatively higher than that of their female counterparts. The possible reasons may be that most of the teacher trainees having high level on teaching competency are using multiple levels of consciousness to apply, manifest and embody spiritual resources, values and qualities in problem solving and attaining goals in ways that enhance their daily functioning and well-being.

- 2 Teaching competency of male teacher trainees affects significantly to their** emotional intelligence or in other words male teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency. Further, the mean score of emotional intelligence of teacher trainees having high level of teaching competency is comparatively higher than that of the teacher trainees having average and low level of teaching competency. The mean score of emotional intelligence of teacher trainees having average level of teaching competency is comparatively higher than that of the teacher trainees having low level of teaching competency and is comparatively less than that of the teacher trainees having high level of teaching competency. The mean score of emotional intelligence of teacher trainees having low level of teaching competency is comparatively less than that of the teacher trainees having high and average level of teaching competency. The possible reasons may be that the male teacher trainees who are comparatively more emotionally stable are more satisfied with their job as well as in their life.
- 3 Teaching competency of female teacher trainees affects significantly to their** emotional intelligence or in other words female teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group differ significantly in terms of their teaching competency. Further, the mean score of emotional intelligence of female teacher trainees having high level of teaching competency is comparatively higher than that of the female teacher trainees having average and low level of teaching competency. The mean score of emotional intelligence of female teacher trainees having average level of teaching competency is comparatively higher than that of the female teacher trainees having low level of teaching competency and is comparatively less than that of the female teacher trainees having high level of teaching competency. The mean score of emotional intelligence of female teacher trainees having low level of teaching competency is comparatively less than that of the female teacher trainees having high and average level of teaching competency. The possible reasons may be that the female teacher trainees who are comparatively more emotionally stable are more satisfied with their job as well as in their life. As the female teacher trainees who have more job security, big amount of salary, high social prestige, less management pressure and no compulsion for involvement in the works other than teaching therefore, they are comparatively more emotionally satisfied with their life.

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